

"MALAYO PA, PERO MALAYO NA": A CASE STUDY OF ELEMENTARY PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS EMOTIONAL EXPERIENCES DURING INTERNSHIP

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Abstract

Teaching Internship is an integral journey for pre-service teachers, providing a platform to apply academic knowledge in the workplace. However, emotional experiences are prevalent during the internship, posing challenges for pre-service teachers. Consequently, this study aims to understand the emotional experiences of pre-service teachers during their internship and assess how it impacts their performance. The current study employed a qualitative method, adhering to a multiple case study design. Ten (10) fourth-year elementary pre-service teachers from Immaculate Conception College of Balayan Inc. were selected using purposive sampling technique. Then thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the data. Results revealed that participants experienced both positive and negative emotional experiences that challenge their self-confidence, time management, teaching abilities, and relationship with cooperating teachers and students. These results indicate that emotional experiences are highly evident during teaching internship. With this, the suggested advocacy plan in this study proposes interventions such as seminars, workshops, and tours to enhance the emotional resilience, emotional support, and emotional management of pre-service teachers. Furthermore, future research is advised to utilize diverse methodological techniques and include a larger sample of pre-service teachers from various majors to encompass broader perspectives on the discussed topic, building upon the findings of the current study.

Keywords: *Emotional experiences, Teaching internship, Pre-service teachers*

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Introduction

Emotional experience is the “constant dialectic relationship between the representation of the outside world and how the world is experienced by the person” (Nogueira, 2014). It deals with how emotions can be developed through experience and at the same time how experiences can be modified because of the person’s emotions. American Psychological Association (APA) stated that emotional experiences consist of three parts: a subjective experience, a physiological response, and a behavioral or expressive response. In addition, Schachter and Singer (1962) theory of emotion, or the two-factor theory of emotion explains that emotions are the product of the interactions of physiological arousal and cognitive interpretation. This theory suggests that the experience of emotions first emerges, followed by a physical response that the mind interprets as the emotion.

“Malayo pa, pero malayo na” is an inspirational quote that has been circulating on social media which means that, “I may be far from my dreams, but I am far enough to be grateful” (Larisma, 2021); that inspires and uplifts many Filipinos, especially the students who have been struggling and fighting in their silent battles. Likewise, experiencing conflicting emotions appeared to be one of the challenges faced by pre-service teachers. During the internship, pre-service teachers experienced positive and negative emotions. However, negative emotions predominated, due to the reality shock of the classroom and its complexity. Their idealistic perceptions of teaching and the actual experiences during the internship contradicted which led to PSTs critical emotional state (Lopez, 2020).

Nevertheless, Internship Program in Philippine Education, mandated by Republic Act 7796, is a prerequisite for graduates before entering the professional world. It refers to the application of academic knowledge in a workplace which aligned with the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) and Commission on Higher Education Memorandum Order (CMO) No. 104, known as the Revised Guidelines for Student Internship Program in the Philippines (SIPP). As stated in Article II, Section 6 of the SIPP, Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs) and Cooperating Schools are pivotal in achieving the program's objectives. This allows students to enhance their formal education with employer-based training to develop life skills essential to contributing to the economy.

Jogan (2019) stated that it is necessary to undergo an internship before graduating to acquire the proficiency of the job that significantly changes the overall behavior and perspective of the pre-service teachers. Most importantly, an internship program increases the employability of students after graduation. It serves as an instrument to prepare students for potential labor force employment nationally or internationally (Tindowen et al., 2019).

Contrary to this, teaching internships were found to expose pre-service teachers to a “high level of burnout”. This occurs as a result of their work-related stressors which affected them to provide satisfactory performance (Samaraweera, 2022). Additionally, Yilong et al. (2022) study found that the negative emotions of the pre-service teachers gradually increased while the positive emotions decreased throughout the months of the practicum. Regardless, pre-service teachers can be confident in their abilities to be successful teachers once they enter the field if they develop strong efficacy beliefs which they can learn from their emotional states (DeMauro & Jennings, 2016).

Taking that into account, it's crucial to consider the pre-service teachers' feelings, apprehensions, and emotional experiences during this period.

Corresponding to this, it was evident that the internship was influential to the pre-service teachers' emotional experiences. However, numerous studies have mainly focused on teachers' and students' emotional responses, not solely on pre-service teachers' emotional experiences (Edwards, 2021; Holappa et al., 2021, as cited in Yilong et al., 2022). In the research locale, pre-service teachers underwent emotional tests and interviews administered by the guidance before the internship. However, some limitations were noted, such as the emotional test was taken online which led to the insufficient validity of the result and PSTs were hesitant to share their experiences during the interview. With this, the current study aimed to further understand the emotional experiences of elementary pre-service teachers and how they coped with the emotional experiences during internship. Furthermore, the study sought to provide an emotional advocacy plan as a basis for further exploration of the study.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to understand the emotional experiences of the pre-service teachers during their internship.

Specifically, this study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What emotional depth do elementary pre-service teachers typically encounter during their internship?
2. What factors contribute to the emotional experiences of elementary pre-service teachers during their internship?
3. In what ways do these emotional experiences impact the performance of elementary pre-service teachers during their internship?
4. How do elementary pre-service teachers cope with and navigate these emotional challenges?
5. What emotional advocacy plan can be formulated for an emotional support tailored to elementary pre-service teachers?

Methodology

The main objective of this study is to understand the emotional experiences of the pre-service teachers during their internship. To attain this, this study employed a multiple case study design under qualitative research. Gustafsson (2017) indicates that multiple case study examined the data across multiple individuals to gain a comprehensive understanding of a wider context. To accomplish this, the researchers conducted an interview with chosen elementary pre-service teachers at Immaculate Conception College of Balayan Inc. who have recently completed their internship and can provide valuable insights into their emotional experiences during this period.

Population and Sampling

The participants of the study consisted of ten (10) fourth-year pre-service teachers at Immaculate Conception College of Balayan Inc. in the academic year 2022-2023. The sampling design used for the study is non-probability

sampling, specifically purposive sampling which is a common sampling used in case studies as suggested by many researchers. With this, the participants that chosen in the study possess the following characteristics: first, exposed to actual teaching practices; second, pre-service teachers who experienced a great extent of emotions during their internship; and third, BEED students of ICCBI who finish the internship training.

Instrumentation

To accomplish the main objective of the research study, the researchers utilized a semi-structured interview to elicit rich and detailed responses from the participants. The interview encompassed five distinct parts: the initial component aimed to establish a comprehensive demographic profile of the participants; the second part was a pivotal question posed to illuminate the myriad emotional experiences elementary pre-service teachers encountered during their internship; the third part delved into the origins of the emotional experiences reported by elementary pre-service teachers; the fourth component consisted of two questions that delved into the positive and negative impacts of emotional experiences on the overall performance of elementary pre-service teachers during their internship; and finally, the fifth part focused on the strategies elementary pre-service teachers employed to overcome the emotional challenges encountered during their internship.

Data Collection

The initial step was approval; the researchers sought permission from the school administration through a request letter. This letter explained the purpose of conducting interviews with BEED graduating students and requested permission to gather data from the guidance office, specifically the results of initial emotional tests and interviews given before the internship. Following approval, an initial survey was conducted using validated yes-or-no questions. This survey was distributed to all BEED 4 students, and those who responded affirmatively regarding experiencing emotional challenges during a teaching internship were selected as participants for the study. Particularly participants from the guidance office who had experienced a range of emotional challenges before their internship and who also responded positively to the pre-survey. Next was the interview preparation. By using a semi-structured interview format, the researchers collected information and data from the participants. The questions were validated by research experts to ensure the instrument's reliability. After that was the interview preparation. The researchers conducted video call interviews with the participants, explaining the purpose of the study and ensuring the confidentiality of their responses. Ample time was provided for participants to answer the questions. Lastly, the gathered data was analyzed and interpreted with the guidance of a research adviser and a language editor. The researchers carefully examined the data, summarized the findings, drew conclusions, made generalizations, and provided recommendations based on the interpretation. Following these steps, the researchers were able to obtain valuable insights from the interviews, ensuring a thorough analysis and interpretation of the collected data.

Data Analysis

To analyze the data, the researchers transcribed the interview responses using Thematic Analysis. Thematic Analysis is a method to analyze qualitative data which is an effective method to interpret people’s views and experiences. By using the following processes— familiarization, coding, generating themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and writing up —the researchers became the instrument for assessing the data gathered (Caulfield, 2023).

Ethical Considerations

The study was conducted with informed consent obtained from the administrator of Immaculate Conception College of Balayan, Inc. It was ensured that participants were fully informed about the voluntary involvement in this study. Furthermore, procedures were followed accordingly, and any data collected during the study were secured with utmost anonymity and confidentiality. To uphold this, participants were assigned code names such as PST 1, PST 2, PST 3, along with the transcribed text from the interview.

Results and Discussions

Below are the findings and data analysis gathered from the responses of 10 participants. Through thematic analysis, several themes emerged regarding the emotional experiences of elementary pre-service teachers during their internship.

Table 1

Emotional Depth that elementary pre-service teachers typically encounter during their internship

Major Themes	Sub-themes	Excerpts
Positive Emotions and Satisfaction	Happy	PST3, PST4, PST5, PST6, PST7, PST8: “But the thing that can make me happy at that times is to see my students gaining knowledge with me ...I have also felt being respected by them and that was a great feeling.”
	Excited	PST8, PST 9, PST10: “Excitement, because of course you will have new learnings given to you by your critique teacher, many tips and advice and strategies will be given to improve your teaching. Of course, there will be children you will meet, love...”
	Satisfied	PST4: “The emotions that I experienced were joy, satisfaction, motivation, stress, frustration, and nervousness.” PST7: “We understand each other, and my classmates have become one of my motivations to continue. They always say, 'You can do it,' and their support means everything to me. We are here for each other.”
	Motivated	
Negative Emotions and Challenges	Sad	PST6, PST7, PST8: “More on sadness, problematic because that time there were so many expenses; Financial problem- Almost all of us in BEED 4- all of us had financial problems. Because the

expenses almost came one after the other and we were still stressed about the thesis then – it brought so much stress to us.”

Frustrated	PST1, PST4, PST10: “I encountered different kinds of challenges like the task that very different than what I expected.”
Nervousness	PST2, PST 4, PST9, PST10: “...I feel so nervous because we are now in a face-to-face class, we’re no longer teaching the children or our classmates through video. I was very nervous when we’re given a subject matter to teach so we must be really prepared and ready before facing the children.”
Pressured	PST3, PST5, PST6: “I was pressured that time because I have felt that I wasn’t meeting the expectation of my mentor.”
Stress	PST3, PST4: “We tend to become stressed when we have a lot of work on our plate. When our subject teacher unexpectedly informs us that we need to create a lesson plan immediately, the materials required for it causes our stress.”
Angry	PST5: “Sometimes I feel angry, but I never let it get to the point where I use hurtful words towards my students. Instead, I make them understand that their bad behavior is unacceptable. I also teach them to set a good example for their classmates by reminding them to apply good manners and show respect towards one another.”

Positive Emotions and Satisfaction; and Negative Emotions and Challenges

The participants were asked about the depth of emotions that they encountered during their internship. It was revealed that the emotions that participants experienced were happy, excited, satisfied, motivated, sad, frustrated, nervousness, pressured, stressed, and angry. The depth of emotions that pre-service teachers experienced spans from positive emotions extending to negative emotions. Some emotions are linked to teaching related emotions while others experienced mixed and various kinds of emotions. With this, two themes emerged: the positive emotions and satisfaction; and the negative emotions and challenges. PST3, PST4, PST5, PST6, PST7, and PST8 felt happy, while PST8, PST9, and PST10 felt excited. PST4 experienced satisfaction, and PST7 felt motivated. On the other hand, PST6, PST7, and PST8 felt sad, while PST1, PST4, and PST10 felt frustrated. Nervousness was commonly felt by PST2, PST4, PST9, and PST10, while PST3, PST5, and PST6 felt pressured. Stress was experienced by PST3 and PST4. Lastly, PST5 felt anger because of the naughtiness of learners.

These findings concur with Belmonte & de la Maya (2023) study which found that positive emotions were established through positive interpersonal relationships with students and successful integration of theory into teaching practices. Conversely, negative emotions arose as a result of low self-perception during interactions within the school community, including colleagues, learners, and school management, and were influenced by emotional processes situated in sociocultural contexts (Nguyen, 2018).

Table 2

Factors that contribute to the emotional experiences of elementary pre-service teachers during their internship

Major Theme	Sub-themes	Excerpts	
Positive Emotional Experience (Internal Factors)	Experienced the practice teaching	PST7: "It's nice to teach because our CT is still there and is kind, and always understands us." PST9: "Excitement, because of course, you will have new learnings given to you by your critique teacher, many tips, advice, and strategies will be given to improve my teaching."	
	Outcome of the lecture delivered that day	PST6: "Maybe it's because of the outcome of a single lecture you gave or something you achieved in one day that seems to make you happy, but it seems to depend on what task you achieved that day."	
	(External Factors)	Bonding with students	PST5: "But the thing that can make me happy at that times is to see my students gaining knowledge with me. I have also felt being respected by them and that was a great feeling." PST9: "... the children (students) I met who love me as their student-teacher. I was happy because they (students) were happy I was there."
		Advice and support of CT	PST7: "I also enjoyed teaching because it's a fulfilling experience to impart knowledge, especially our CT is kind and understanding. It's a great feeling to know that we are ready to be understood."
Negative Emotional Experience (Internal Factors)	Sympathizing with co-preservice teachers	PST3: "...we feel happy when we're on the field, and we enjoy teaching. Perhaps it's just that when we express ourselves (communicate), we tend to talk about situations that upset us. We share our feelings with our colleagues, and comfort each other." PST7: "My co-pre service teachers (source of positive emotion) because we sympathize with each other."	
	Lack of Time	PST1, PST3, PST4, PST6, PST7, PST8, PST9: "I lose focus, I can't do what I should do because of my emotions and workload."	
	Pressured	PST3: "Mixed emotions, because sometimes there are times that are stressful and there are also times when we break down from too much work. Pressured." PST6: "The first thing that hit me immediately was the pressure. The teachers' expectations are the main reason because they always say, 'You're good at it, but you should be better so we can't be disappointed!'" PST8: "I experienced breakdown because I feel pressured because I was being compared by other pre -service teacher from another school."	
	(External Factors)	Transition to the new environment	PST10: "The causes of my emotions are the new environment and the transition from the school setting to professional work."
(External Factors)	Heavy workloads including the making of Instructional Materials	PST1, PST3, PST4, PST 6, PST7, PST8, PST9: "We get stressed when we have a lot of work. The subject teacher surprises us that we need to make a lesson plan immediately. Then those materials are the causes of our stress."	

Teachers and family expectations	<p>PST 5: "I have been pressured also that time because I have felt that I wasn't meeting the expectation of my CT."</p> <p>PST6: "I felt sadness because the pressure seems to be mixed up. Of course, when you are under pressure you will be sad... The teachers' expectations are the main reason because they always say, 'You're good at it, but you should be better so we can't be disappointed'."</p> <p>PST8: "I experienced breakdown because I feel pressured because I was being compared by other pre -service teacher from another school. I need to keep up with the expectations of my CT."</p> <p>PST9: "...the performance expectations made me pressured, anxious and stressed which is I don't know how to manage them immediately".</p>
Handling multiple class	<p>PST4: "The cause of my emotions was the heavy workload because during my fs 7 I handled forty students from section 1 to section 6."</p> <p>PST 10: "I handled different kinds of class even though I started from the grade1 then I have to go to grade 6, the pattern is not successive."</p>
Comparison Pressure	<p>PST5: "I was also stressed and feeling pressured as there was a time that I was being compared to other student teacher like me that I need to do better as what others did."</p> <p>PST8: "During my demo teaching, I received a comment from my cooperating teacher which made me feel sad. I experienced a breakdown as I was being compared to another pre-service teacher from another school."</p>
Financial Problems	<p>PST7: "Almost all of us in BEED 4- all of us had financial problems. Because the expenses almost came one after another."</p>
Handling Naughty Learners	<p>PST5: "My emotions caused during my internship is the naughtiness of my learners but luckily, I am able to cope it."</p>

Positive Emotional Experience (Internal Factors and External Factors)

Pre-service teachers shared numerous factors that highly contribute to the emotions they experience during their internship. Based on the data, two themes emerged: Positive Emotional Experiences, which are divided into Internal and External Factors, and Negative Emotional Experiences, which are also divided into Internal and External Factors. In these major themes, the emotions from the findings in Table 1 and the causes of emotions in Table 2 intersect, resulting in both positive and negative emotional experiences.

In the first theme, internal factors or the positive emotions because of oneself, participants highlighted certain emotions that fostered their confidence and motivation during the internship. PST7 and PST 9 stated that they felt excitement because they got to experience practice teaching. Similarly, PST10 felt excitement because of the outcome of the lecture delivered that day. On the other hand, in the external factors or the influence of the environment to cause positive emotions, PST5 and PST9 felt happiness because the students' gain of knowledge from them. Then PST7 felt supported and understood by the Cooperating Teacher, which strengthened his/her confidence. Lastly, PST3 and PST7 were grateful to have the support of their co-preservice teacher, reminding them that they were not alone.

Therefore, positive emotional experiences, both internal and external factors, fostered the professional identity development of every pre-service teacher. PSTs' professional identities were developed during their field teaching experience, which strengthened their commitment to the teaching profession; it fosters their emotions by receiving good feedback from others. Yang et al. (2019) suggests that pre-service teachers' emotional patterns are currently considered an important area of study. Pre-service teachers' strong emotions, both positive and negative, were shaped by their internal characteristics and the sociocultural environments they encountered in school. Therefore, PSTs' internship experiences had a significant emotional impact on their development.

Negative Emotional Experience (Internal Factors and External Factors)

In the second theme, PSTs also shared the factors that caused their negative emotions during their internship. Participants elaborated that these factors led them to be emotionally unstable during their internship.

In internal factors, seven participants (PST1, PST3, PST4, PST 6, PST7, PST8, PST9) mentioned that heavy workload was the main source of their stress and pressure. They stated that it was hard to focus and finish the task when it was simultaneously given. With this PST3, PST6, and PST8 felt pressured not just by workloads but also by dealing with high expectations. Then PST10, on the other hand, struggled on adjusting to the new environment. PST10 shared that it was difficult to be overwhelmed by the responsibilities of being a teacher. However, despite the negative emotions, they were still consistent in their role as a pre-service teacher.

On the other hand, participants shared the external factors that contributed to their negative emotional experiences. Thus, these are the causes of their emotions from their environment. Seven participants (PST1, PST3, PST4, PST 6, PST7, PST8, PST9) shared the struggle of having enormous workloads especially when the lesson needed to be executed the next day and the need to prepare the instructional materials. PST5, 6, 8, and PST9 struggles in experiencing high expectation from their family and CTs. Thus, they do their best to meet their CTs' standards and expectations however it loses their confidence.

Then, PST4 and PST10 had a hard time handling multiple class. PST5 and PST8 shared that it was difficult to be compared to other pre-service teachers from other schools while PST7 stated that the major cause of her negative emotions was financial worries. Conversely, PST5 claimed that the misbehavior of the students was the reason behind his/her negative emotions. With this, the negative emotional experiences led them to feel helpless and it caused them to lose self-confidence. Although this is common to all pre-service teachers, they accept that those negative emotions are given especially during internship and they cope with it through their own various coping strategies.

Additionally, when the PSTs began learning about evaluating students, they felt a wide range of emotions, positive and negative, and these were observed to act as filters and amplifiers for their classroom practices (Edwards, 2019). Therefore, despite the factors that contributed to their emotional experience during their internship they still had the conviction to overcome it regardless of the negative emotions they were experiencing. PSTs' goal is to showcase the real-world teaching behind various emotions they were experiencing.

Table 3

Positive impact of emotional experiences on the internship performance of elementary pre-service teachers

Major Themes	Sub-themes	Excerpts
Positive Impact (Internal Stimuli)	Motivated to achieve their goals	PST1: "...my emotion motivates me to achieve my goals. For example, I'm going to have a breakdown right now because I have a lot to do, so my emotions are what motivate me so I just think about finishing what I'm doing." PST6: "The positive thing about it is that every emotion I felt I turned it into motivation..." PST7: "The positive effect of my emotions on my performance is- I was more motivated as if I could do better, that I would do my best as time went by..." PST8: "I feel motivated to prove myself and to other people that I should do well because nothing will happen if I let my emotion affect me."
	Confident in teaching and prepared	PST2: "Full of confidence before going to bed, before going to school, you must be prepared and ready for what you will teach the children..."
	Enthusiastic	PST10: "During my internship the positive effects on my emotions are the enthusiasm, my passion for teaching and the genuine excitement that being in the classroom that fueled my motivation to drive to myself."
Positive Impact (External Stimuli)	Overcome stress by having deep talks with the cooperating teacher	PST3: "Maybe I experienced what can be called a deal (with Cooperating Teacher) because we easily overcame our stress because we went with the same situation during our FS 2."
	Success in the subsequent Demonstration Teaching	PST4: "I thought I couldn't do it because before I entered my internship, I was having a hard time in my practice demo teaching. Then when I did my last demo teaching during my fs 7 it was successful"
	Able to handle the class professionally	PST5: "... it helps me to be a better individual as I slowly learn and apply it within myself. I was able to handle the class professionally."

Positive Impact

Internal Stimuli

Participants in the study experienced different kinds of emotions in their role as pre-service teachers. The elementary PSTs talked about how this may affect their performance during the internship. Four participants (PST 1, PST 6, PST 7, PST 8) articulated that they felt motivated to achieve their goals which resulted success in terms of their teaching demonstration. PST 2 also noted that being confident and be prepared in teaching is very significant so that the flow of the lesson is continuous and the children can follow you. Moreover, PST 10 stated that they felt enthusiastic

because his/her passion for teaching and the genuine excitement that being in the classroom that fueled his/her motivation.

In relation to this, Mulang (2021) remarked that positive emotion particularly being highly motivated teacher can easily attain their goals and accomplish tasks that can result in great performance. With this, it was proven that being motivated greatly affect the pre-service teachers’ performance in their internship. Therefore, positive emotions that pre-service teacher experience influenced their performance specifically in their teaching demonstration. In this part, it shows that the participants in this study felt motivated, confident, prepared, and enthusiastic which resulted in their good performance during their internship.

External Stimuli

The second theme refers to external stimuli that are directly related to the environment that the pre-service teacher experienced during their internship. PST 3 shared that their cooperating teacher helps them to overcome their stress. Moreover, PST 4 stated that through his/her emotion their last demo teaching was successful. PST 5 also stated that emotion help his/her to be a better individual which resulted to handle the class professionally. These participants admitted that at first, they had doubts on their selves but then they realized that if they let their negative emotions affect them it would only cause unfavorable outcomes in their performance during their internship so they took those emotions positively resulting into successful performance during their internship.

Similarly, Hagen et al. (2022) noted that student teachers demonstrated characteristics that transformed their experience, and cooperating teachers acknowledged these qualities of their student teachers. As a result, they were more willing to share teaching responsibilities and form personal connections, resulting in more comfortable teaching-working conditions. Therefore, expected emotion like stress during internship is a conventional situation for the pre-service teacher. Based on the responses of the participants it was clearly stated that the cooperating teacher (CT) always plays a significant role in their internship not just in their teaching performance as well as in their emotion during their internship.

Table 4

Negative impact of emotional experiences on the internship performance of elementary pre-service teachers

Major Theme	Sub-themes	Excerpts
Negative Impact (Internal Stimuli)	Lose focus and get mentally blocked while teaching	PST1: "I cried a lot, like I was out of my wit. Like what I'm teaching seems like I don't know. You know what you're going to teach them (students) but you feel wrong about it." PST2: "During my first demonstration, I was nervous and mentally blocked even though I was prepared."
	Lack of Confidence while Teaching	PST3: "I have this thought in myself that others think less of me and judge me. It always circulates in my mind but maybe it's just all in my mind."

		PST7: "...because of expenses that come one after another, I was unable to focus on my teaching. I was at the point where I was lost. I just wanted to be absent."
Negative Impact (External Stimuli)	Felt pressured and anxious while teaching Experienced frustration because of the unresponsiveness of students	PST10: "I felt anxious because of the responsibility and expectations associated with being a teacher." PST10: Students were not responsive to my teaching methods and the lesson did not go up to plan. I became frustrated and I lost my confidence in my abilities.
	Felt pressured because of expectations of teachers and family	PST5: "I was pressured at that time because I felt that I wasn't meeting the expectations of my mentor (CT)." PST6: "They always expect my performance to be good and pleasing. Like I need to meet their expectations always – not just my CT but everyone including my family."
	Insufficient time in preparing Instructional Materials and Lesson Plans	PST3, PST4, PST9: "I can't handle the stress, especially in making materials because once we're given a subject matter, I have to do it right away because I will be teaching it the next day." PST6: "I cried because I felt pressured, especially when it came to the instructional materials. What made it difficult for me was if the time would be enough." PST8: "It was stressful because of the time(schedule) that was given to us for our demo teaching. I don't know which one to prioritize... Instead of thinking about the materials that I would use, my emotions got me first."
	Revision of Lesson Plans	PST9: "...immediately creating my lesson plan because the day before I teach it, it needs to be checked by my CT. If something is wrong, I need to revise it until my CT is satisfied with the LP." PST4: I encountered a different format than what I learned in school. At times, I would submit my lesson plan, only to realize later that I had made errors, leading to the need for revisions.

Negative Impact

Internal Stimuli

The participants were asked about the negative impact of their emotional experiences on their performance during their internship, and it was revealed that these experiences had a detrimental effect on their internship performance. Upon examining the participants' responses, one of the themes emerged was the internal stimuli that explains the experiences of emotions that occur within the person. During the internship, PST1 and PST2 shared that experiencing negative emotions caused them to lose focus and become mentally blocked while teaching. PST3 and PST7 stated that they felt a lack of self-confidence and felt pressured, while PST10 felt anxious while teaching.

Given that PSTs were completing their internships and exposed to the teaching profession, participants were accustomed to being overwhelmed by the related responsibilities of being a teacher. Therefore, the emotional states

that occur within pre-service teachers cause numerous obstructions to their teaching performance. External factors, which are uncontrollable, serve as the source of emotions within the self of the PSTs, leading to a negative impact on their internship performance. In other words, negative emotions arise due to environmental factors that adversely affect the PSTs' performances. Correspondingly, Yan and Mingyao (2022) discussed that during practicum, PSTs discovered that teachers' responsibilities are more multifarious and diverse. Throughout the process, PSTs are inevitably confronted with problems that weaken their confidence and willingness to be teachers, eventually influencing how they feel about themselves.

External Stimuli

On the other hand, another theme that emerged was External Stimuli, which explains that people from the environment were influential in the internship performance of the PSTs. PST10 experienced frustration because of the unresponsiveness of students. PST5 and PST6 felt pressured because of the expectations of their family and teachers. While PST3, PST4, PST6, PST8, and PST9 experienced insufficient time in preparing Instructional Materials (IMS) and Lesson Plans (LP). Then PST4 and PST9 stressed the Revision of Lesson Planning.

This is closely aligned with the study of Yang (2019, as cited in Edwards, 2021), which indicated that depending on how feedback was given, PSTs felt a depth of emotional responses (e.g., worry, confidence, self-efficacy). Furthermore, academic demands appear to contradict the pre-service teachers' motivation. PSTs experience stress due to the discrepancy between the evaluation process and the skills necessary to become a proficient teacher. As a result, obstacles in the training process become apparent in the PSTs' first teaching experiences (Núñez-Regueiro et al., 2023).

In a nutshell, the people in the environment, including the students, CT, and family, have contributed to how well the PSTs executed their internship performance. Although it was hard for them to deal with their emotions (e.g., frustration, pressure, breakdown) at that time, and even though their initial practice teachings did not proceed as planned, they admitted that they performed well on their internship performance in their subsequent practice teachings. As a result, the unplanned and dissatisfied outcomes with their internship performance served as their motivation to do well in their upcoming practice teachings.

Table 5

Coping Strategies that elementary pre-service teachers used to navigate the emotional challenges that they encountered during Internship

Major Theme	Sub-themes	Codes
Personal Coping Strategies	Training oneself to be independent and to be prepared	PST6: "Your friends won't help you totally – yes, they are there but you have to train yourself to be yourself. It's like you need to be independent and not always depend on other people."
	Motivation and confidence in oneself	PST1: "I use it as motivation, I can't just be stuck in that situation because I won't be able to finish."

		PST2: "Don't be nervous, before I enter the classroom, I remind myself to be confident so while I'm teaching, the flow will be continuous."
	Self-awareness	<p>PST5: "I overcome it by being careful not to throw hurtful words at my students since children are sensitive."</p> <p>PST6: "My experience is that I only motivate myself to succeed in what I do, like when there are demonstrations every week- no matter how many they are."</p> <p>PST10: "...I recognized my knowledge and my emotions. To be aware and understand the impact of my performance and also seek support and guidance."</p>
	Praying	<p>PST6: "I have talked to many people. I talked to my friends, boyfriend, parents, and especially God..."</p> <p>PST7: "First of all, prayer – I really prayed and prayed to the Lord. Then second because of my classmates, my CT who encouraged me. Third is myself."</p> <p>PST9: "I overcome my emotions through the help of our Lord, of course, family and friends."</p>
	Watching movies and motivational videos	<p>PST4: "All I have is myself. I always motivate myself that I can do it. I shared my experiences with my friends and my hobbies are watching k-drama and watching tiktoks to keep my mind entertained."</p> <p>PST5: "...I was just watching some motivational videos in where I can relate of and it makes me motivated to do more."</p>
	Listening to music	PST8: "...I calm myself so that I feel relieved. I listen to music and sleep."
	Treating oneself after a successful demonstration	PST6: "Apart from that, I didn't celebrate my successful demo every week because we had a dry run there, I only celebrated when I had my final demonstration...."
	Playing online games	PST6: "Another thing is hobbies like ML and k-drama but I do those things rarely."
	Sleep	PST8: "...I calm myself so that I feel relieved. I listen to music and sleep."
Social Coping Strategies	Rely on family and friends help, love, and support	PST4: "I overcome that with the help and love of my family. There are people who guide me. I didn't feel like I was alone. My professor helped me a lot to be better."
	Share experiences with classmates	<p>PST3: "Perhaps we express our emotions by articulating what upsets us, and when we share our feelings with our colleagues, we provide each other with comfort and support."</p> <p>PST8: "I told my best friend about those experiences during my internship. She gives me pieces of advice regarding the things that I need to do. She said that I should calm myself..."</p> <p>PST9: "I overcame it through the help of our Lord, of course, my family and friends because the best and happiest thing of all is when someone believes in you that you can do it."</p>

Seek helpful advice from professors and cooperating teachers

PST4: "I didn't feel like I was alone. My professor helped me a lot to be better."

PST7: "I have my CT who encouraged me..."

PST10: I reach out at the guidance or mentors to discuss my concerns – anxiety about the upcoming lessons."

Personal Coping Strategies

Pre-service teachers employ various strategies to overcome the negative emotional experiences that they encountered during their internship. Under the theme of personal coping strategies, various pre-service teachers share how they cope with emotional challenges based on their own strategies. PST6 copes with negative emotions by training themselves to be independent and prepared. Additionally, PST1 and PST2 state that they motivate themselves by having confidence in their abilities, which they use as a driving force to finish their internship. Meanwhile, PST5, PST6, and PST10 underscore the importance of self-awareness and being mindful of their actions and words during their internship. Moreover, PST6, PST7, and PST9 discuss how praying helps them share the emotions they experience with God. PST 4 and PST5 cite that they watch movies and motivational videos during their free time, while PST6 mentioned that treating oneself after a successful demonstration and playing online games is very helpful to distract themselves once in a while. Lastly, PST8 notes that sleeping can help to alleviate their emotions and make them feel relieved.

Aligned with this, Çakmak et al. (2019) investigated the challenges encountered by pre-service teachers and the coping strategies they employed to overcome them. According to this study, coping mechanisms include altering one's surroundings, engaging in active conversation, and using internal peace techniques. Whether making major or minor decisions, PSTs benefit from emotional regulation. Comprehending emotions enables an individual to recognize triggers and acquire knowledge of constructive methods to react. Therefore, in order to overcome challenges, pre-service teachers must use coping mechanisms such effective communication, inner peace strategies, and environment adjustment. Individuals who continue utilizing these kinds of tactics can acquire the emotional intelligence and resilience needed to succeed in the teaching profession.

Social Coping Strategies

In this theme, social coping strategies, participants seek emotional support based on their social interaction and reliance with family, peers, and teachers. In this theme on social coping strategies, participants seek emotional support through their social interactions and relationships with family, peers, and teachers. PST4 shared that they rely on the help, love, and support of their family and friends, which they use as motivation to continue pursuing their passions. Meanwhile, PST3, PST8, and PST9 stated that they share their experiences with classmates to help relieve their stress. Additionally, PST4, PST7, and PST10 seek helpful advice from professors and cooperating teachers to broaden their understanding of how to be more professional in the teaching field.

According to Yayli (2017), it was widely accepted that one of the most important coping methods was to rely on significant persons (e.g., family, friends, classmates, CT, professors) at stressful moments for discussion and

reflection. When PSTs believe in one other and form relationships, they feel a great deal better with the support of those around them. PSTs are reminded by this that they are not alone and that there are individuals who respect and care about them. As a result, the PSTs successfully manage their emotions throughout their internship by utilizing these social coping techniques. Connecting with loved ones, friends, and fellow students facilitated the sharing of issues, feelings, and firsthand experiences from their internship, as well as solutions to these concerns. Professors and cooperating teachers also provide them with guidance by fostering a relationship of trust and by setting an example that helps them advance as teachers.

Table 6
Proposed Advocacy Plan

Emotional Advocacy Plan for incoming 4th year Pre-service Teachers

Area of Concern	Objective	Activities/ Action Taken	Target Date	Persons Involved	Resource/ Budget	Expected Outcomes
Emotional Resilience	Enhancing awareness about multifaceted aspects of teaching internship by fostering emotional development on pre-service teachers.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Organize and propose a seminar discussing topics about the overview of teaching internship and its importance, a guide for teaching resilience and emotional well-being empowerment, lasty discussing effective emotional coping strategies to regulate negative emotional experiences. 2. Collaborate with mental health professionals/ counselors and professors/teachers who can offer in-depth discussions regarding the seminar's content. 3. Arrange meetings and bide till the approval is granted. Subsequently, disseminate the information/material with the seminar attendees and the involved facilitators. 	January 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All incoming 4th year pre-service teachers who will undergo internship - School Administration and facilitators of Education Department - Guest speakers (Mental health professionals/ counselors & Professors/ teachers) 	Budget for Education and Training	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthened self-awareness by recognizing one's emotions and how these emotions can affect their internship performance. 2. Planned and created a classroom management approaches, teaching strategies, lists of teaching materials, etc. that strengthened PSTs preparation for the teaching internship. 3. Integrated emotional coping strategies to effectively regulate their own emotions leaving a significant and beneficial impact on their internship performance.
Emotional Support	Enhance pre-service teachers' emotional regulation, effective stress management, strengthened interpersonal skills and also given the knowledge, abilities, and attitudes needed to build emotional ce and prove overall well-being.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Conducting a team-building exercises promoting collaboration and communication. - It can improve pre-service teachers' interpersonal skills, trust, and ability to work together by encouraging cooperation and communication. 2. Making expressive arts such as drawing, composing music or poems and writing as a means of constructive emotional expression. 	February 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All incoming 4th year pre-service teachers who will undergo internship - School Administration and facilitators of Education Department 	Budget for Education and Training	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Developed pre-service teachers' interpersonal skills by creating support systems among pre-service teachers strengthened with shared experiences and inclusive environment. 2. Fostered empathy towards others and improved the PSTs self-awareness. 3. Increased confidence upbrining the personal and professional growth of pre-

service teachers and its application in teaching internship.

- Pre-service teachers can find that creating art, music, or writing are effective ways to communicate their emotions in a healthy way, handle difficult emotions, and express themselves in ways that go beyond conventional verbal communication by participating in these creative ways.

- Guest speakers/Facilitators (Mental health professionals/counselors & Professors/teachers)

3. There will be a reflection session about their emotional experiences to establish their trust.

- Explore and analyze their own experiences in the context of establishing trust within educational settings during reflection sessions on personal experiences connected to trust-building.

Emotional Management

Improving awareness and understanding in terms emotional management of pre-service teachers as they undergo their internship program.

1. Take pre-service teachers on a school tour that will help them gain more knowledge about on how to regulate their emotions by visiting multiple places.

2. Offer activities in various places where pre-service elementary teachers can discuss and explore their emotions as well as share their experiences coping with them.

3. Raise awareness of the significance of recognizing and managing one's emotions by participating in seminars when the guest speaker is a mental health advocate, counsellor, or other expert with relevant expertise who can comprehensively discuss the tour's context.

March 2025

- All incoming 4th year pre-service teachers who will undergo internship

- School Administration and facilitators of Education Department

- Partnered destinations/organization/company

Budget for Education and Training

1. Increased growth on personal as well as professional grounds as a result of understanding their emotional experiences.

2. Incorporated emotional intelligence in teaching practices as they handled novel challenges in the internship.

3. Progressively participated in the partnered-school by carrying out what was learned in the tour. Displayed a positive relationship with the cooperating teachers, students, and co-preservice teachers.

Advocacy Plan to Empower the Emotional Well-being of Pre-Service Teachers during Internship

The proposed advocacy plan serves as a basis to empower the emotional well-being of the pre-service teachers during internship. This advocacy plan focuses on enhancing emotional resilience, fostering emotional support, and improving emotional management. Each areas serve a purpose to bring emotional empowerment to all upcoming 4th year pre-service teachers before entering teaching internship.

The first are of concern, "Emotional Resilience," highlights the importance of seminars to strengthen the readiness of PSTs before entering internship. Through seminars, it aims to enhance awareness about multifaceted aspects of teaching internship such as in planning a classroom management approaches, teaching strategies, and emotional coping strategies to regulate one's emotion.

The second area of concern, "Emotional Support," adhere to foster PSTs effective stress management, strengthened interpersonal skills and also to build emotional intelligence to improve overall well-being. Through team building, expressive arts, and reflection session it upbrings the PSTs interpersonal skills, fostered empathy towards others and improve self-awareness. It also aims to increased personal and professional growth of pre-service teachers and its application in teaching internship.

The third area of concern, "Emotional Management," upbrings awareness and understanding in terms of emotional management of pre-service teachers as they will undergo internship program. By having a school tour, it will help them gain more knowledge about on how to regulate their emotions by visiting multiple places which also offers various activities. It also raises awareness of the significance of recognizing and managing one's emotions by participating in seminar where the guest speaker is a mental health advocate, counselor, or expert with relevant expertise who can comprehensively discuss the tour's context.

Overall, the advocacy plan designed in this study presents aspects to effectively recognize, empowered, and manage the emotions of the PSTs by increasing their readiness in the tiring but worthwhile journey in teaching internship. The proposed advocacy plan is not intended to be put into practice but rather a recommendation serving as the basis for further investigation. This study aimed to contribute to the existing discourse on the emotional experiences of pre-service teachers during their teaching internship; suggesting other researchers to delve deeper into the identified and limited insinuation discussed in the study.

Conclusions

The elementary pre-service teachers experienced emotional depth during their internship, from negative to positive emotions. The findings of the study emphasized that these emotions were linked to teaching-related emotions, while other pre-service teachers experienced mixed and various kinds of emotions.

The emotional experiences of elementary pre-service teachers were influenced by several factors, including heavy workload, challenges in supervising and teaching pupils, financial constraints, emotional support, excitement,

anxiety, performance expectations, and adjusting to a new environment. These factors challenged their abilities during the teaching internship, but also increased their confidence in their ability to teach.

Moreover, emotional experiences were highly influential on the internship performance of elementary pre-service teachers. Positive Factors brought satisfaction in PSTs teaching performance; whereas Negative Factors set drawbacks in the initial teaching practices. However, in PSTs subsequent teaching practices became successful as the participants turned their negative emotional experiences as an inspiration for improvement.

Despite the emotional challenges, the elementary pre-service teachers navigated them by using multiple coping strategies. Personal and social coping strategies helped pre-service teachers elevate their teaching internship performance, improving both their personal and professional growth in the teaching field.

Furthermore, the emotional test and interview conducted by the Guidance Office aligns with the findings of the researchers. As a result, it is evident that intense emotional experiences are prevalent among elementary pre-service teachers before and during their internship. In light of this, the emotional advocacy proposed in this study seeks to proactively address these challenges. The proposed initiatives aim to enhance the resilience, emotional support, and emotional management skills of pre-service teachers. These measures are intended to better prepare pre-service teachers for their teaching internship and improve their readiness for teaching practices.

Recommendations

Pre-service teachers experienced a depth of both positive and negative emotions during their internship, posing challenges to their capabilities in teaching. In light of this, it is recommended for pre-service teachers to participate in training sessions and seminars aimed at fostering personal and professional development with a specific focus on emotional empowerment. Such initiatives may aid in the construction of their professional identity and enhance their ability to effectively navigate and address challenges encountered during their internship.

It is also suggested for cooperating teachers to establish a positive mentorship with pre-service teachers. This approach aims to enhance the learning experiences of PSTs to foster a positive relationship that supports and strengthens the emotional well-being of pre-service teachers. In addition, research readers are urged to have an awareness of the context to offer mutual support and to contribute for a positive and empathetic environment. Parents are also encouraged to acknowledge the depth of emotions that pre-service teachers experience during their teaching internship. It would be highly beneficial to actively listen to PSTs' concerns, provide comfort, and offer support.

Moreover, college instructors are recommended to integrate emotional intelligence and management into coursework to prepare pre-service teachers for challenging situations during teaching internships. This integration is to offer pre-service teachers with essential skills to handle emotional challenges effectively, enhancing their readiness for the demands of teaching. Additionally, it is recommended that school counselors collaborate with school administrators to extend emotional assessments and offer counseling services that are specifically tailored for emotions of pre-service teachers. This collaborative effort aims to continually monitor and assess the emotional situations of pre-

service teachers throughout their internships. It seeks to establish preventive measures to assist the emotional well-being of pre-service teachers.

For school administrators it is recommended to facilitate workshops, training sessions, and emotional programs designed to address the needs of students in navigating emotional challenges during their internships. Collaborating with the school guidance is necessary to implement a comprehensive and systematic program tailored to enhance the emotional resilience of pre-service teachers in teaching internships.

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